

Big Data to Enable Global Disruption of the Grapevine-powered Industries

D4.3 - Models and Tools for Predictive Analytics over Extremely Large Datasets

DELIVERABLE NUMBER	D4.3
DELIVERABLE TITLE	Models and Tools for Predictive Analytics over Extremely Large Datasets
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Franco Maria Nardini (CNR)

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020
Framework Programme of the European Union

GRANT AGREEMENT N.	780751
PROJECT ACRONYM	BigDataGrapes
PROJECT FULL NAME	Big Data to Enable Global Disruption of the Grapevine-powered industries
STARTING DATE (DUR.)	01/01/2018 (36 months)
ENDING DATE	31/12/2020
PROJECT WEBSITE	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/
COORDINATOR	Nikos Manouselis
ADDRESS	110 Pentelis Str., Marousi, GR15126, Greece
REPLY TO	nikosm@agroknow.com
PHONE	+30 210 6897 905
EU PROJECT OFFICER	Mr. Riku Leppanen
WORKPACKAGE N. TITLE	WP4 Analytics and Processing Layer
WORKPACKAGE LEADER	CNR
DELIVERABLE N. TITLE	D4.3 Models and Tools for Predictive Analytics over Extremely Large Datasets
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Franco Maria Nardini (CNR)
REPLY TO	francomaria.nardini@isti.cnr.it
DOCUMENT URL	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/
DATE OF DELIVERY (CONTRACTUAL)	30 September 2018 (M9)
DATE OF DELIVERY (SUBMITTED)	First version: 28 September 2018 (M9) Update 1: 15 April 2019 (M15) Update 2: 30 July 2020 (M31)
VERSION STATUS	3.0 Final
NATURE	DEM (Demonstrator)
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PU (Public)
AUTHORS (PARTNER)	Franco Maria Nardini (CNR), Vinicius Monteiro de Lira (CNR), Salvatore Trani (CNR), Raffaele Perego (CNR), Cristina Muntean (CNR)
CONTRIBUTORS	Ioanna Polychronou (Agroknow), Katerina Kasimati (AUA)
REVIEWER	Simone Parisi (ABACO), Nyi-Nyi Htun (KU Leuven)

VERSION	MODIFICATION(S)	DATE	AUTHOR(S)
0.1	Initial contributions	04/09/2018	Vinicius Monteiro de Lira (CNR), Franco Maria Nardini (CNR), Nicola Tonello (CNR)
0.2	Added contributions	07/09/2018	Vinicius Monteiro de Lira (CNR), Franco Maria Nardini (CNR)
0.3	Input from partners integrated, document almost finalized	14/09/2018	Franco Maria Nardini (CNR), Raffaele Perego (CNR), Cristina Muntean (CNR), Ida Mele (CNR), Salvatore Trani (CNR)
0.4	Internal Review	16/09/2018	Simone Parisi (ABACO)
1.0	Partners review, final comments and edits	28/09/2018	Franco Maria Nardini (CNR), Raffaele Perego (CNR), Cristina Muntean (CNR), Ida Mele (CNR), Salvatore Trani (CNR)
1.1	Added contributions for updated version	15/04/2019	Vinicius Monteiro de Lira (CNR), Franco Maria Nardini (CNR), Raffaele Perego (CNR), Cristina Muntean (CNR), Nicola Tonello (CNR), Salvatore Trani (CNR)
1.1	Internal Review	12/04/2019	Nyi-Nyi Htun (KU Leuven)
2.0	Partners review, final comments and edits	15/04/2019	Vinicius Monteiro de Lira (CNR), Franco Maria Nardini (CNR), Raffaele Perego (CNR), Cristina Muntean (CNR), Nicola Tonello (CNR), Salvatore Trani (CNR)
2.1	Added contributions for updated version	15/07/2020	Vinicius Monteiro de Lira (CNR), Franco Maria Nardini (CNR), Raffaele Perego (CNR), Salvatore Trani (CNR), Ioanna Polychronou (AgroKnow), Katerina Kasimati (AUA)
2.2	Internal Review	25/07/2020	Nyi-Nyi Htun (KU Leuven)
3.0	Final comments and edits	27/07/2020	Franco Maria Nardini (CNR)

PARTICIPANTS		CONTACT
<p>Agroknow IKE (Agroknow, Greece)</p>		<p>Nikos Manouselis Email: nikosm@agroknowc.com</p>
<p>Ontotext AD (ONTOTEXT, Bulgaria)</p>		<p>Todor Primov Email: todor.primov@ontotext.com</p>
<p>Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche (CNR, Italy)</p>		<p>Raffaele Perego Email: raffaele.perego.isti.cnr.it</p>
<p>Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KULeuven, Belgium)</p>		<p>Katrien Verbert Email: katrien.verbert@cs.kuleuven.be</p>
<p>Geocledian GmbH (GEOCLEDIAN Germany)</p>		<p>Stefan Scherer Email: stefan.scherer@geocledian.com</p>
<p>Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique (INRAE, France)</p>		<p>Pascal Neveu Email: pascal.neveu@inra.fr</p>
<p>Agricultural University of Athens (AUA, Greece)</p>		<p>Katerina Biniari Email: kbiniari@aua.gr</p>
<p>Abaco SpA (ABACO, Italy)</p>		<p>Simone Parisi Email: s.parisi@abacogroup.eu</p>
<p>SYMBEEOSIS EY ZHN S.A. (Symbeeosis, Greece)</p>	 <p>Symbeeosis</p>	<p>Konstantinos Rodopoulos Email: rodopoulos-k@symbeeosis.com</p>

ACRONYMS LIST

BDG	BigDataGrapes
HDFS	Hadoop Distributed File System
RDD	Resilient Distributed Dataset
TF-IDF	Term Frequency – Inverse Document Frequency
GBT	Gradient Boosting Trees
DT	Decision Trees
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This accompanying document for deliverable D4.3 (Models and Tools for Predictive Analytics over Extremely Large Datasets) describes the first version of the mechanisms and tools supporting efficient and effective predictive data analytics over the BigDataGrapes (BDG) platform in the context of grapevine-related assets.

The BDG software stack employs efficient and fault-tolerant tools for distributed processing, aimed at providing scalability and reliability for the target applications. On top of this stack, the BDG platform enables distributed predictive big data analytics by effectively exploiting scalable Machine Learning algorithms using the computational resources of the underlying infrastructure efficiently. The software components enabling BDG predictive data analytics have been designed and deployed using Docker containers¹. They thus include everything needed to run the supported predictive data analytics tools on any system that can run a Docker engine.

The document first introduces the main technologies currently used in the first version of the BDG component for performing efficient and scalable analytics over extremely large dataset. The docker component provided in this deliverable relies on the BDG software stack discussed in Deliverable 2.3: “BigDataGrapes Software Stack Design” and exploits the distributed execution environment provided by the Persistence and Processing Layers of the BDG architecture contributed in Deliverable 4.1: “Methods and Tools for Scalable Distributed Processing”.

In Section 3, we detail the steps to be followed to download and deploy the first version of the BDG platform and provides the reader with practical examples of usage of its scalable predictive analytics component. Specifically, we provide four demonstrators released as Jupyter Notebooks² implementing four different machine learning tasks by exploiting the BDG infrastructure. The first one shows how to train two kinds of regressors, i.e., linear and random forest regressors, to fit synthetically generated data. We present these results by adding a visualization of the result to allow the reader to understand the limitations of each specific solution. The second demonstrator employs a well-known dataset, i.e., the KDD CUP 1999 dataset³, to train a binary logistic regression classifier. We show how to train and evaluate the performance of the classifier by means of a standard metric, i.e., Accuracy. This second demonstrator also shows how the distributed file system can be exploited to directly feed the machine learning platform with data. The third demonstrator extends the second one by showing how to train a multi-label classifier on a Red Wine Quality Dataset⁴, a public dataset employed on Kaggle for a machine learning competition. We show how to learn a multi-label logistic regression classifier and how to evaluate its performance in terms of Accuracy.

Section 3 also presents a fourth demonstrator, which is much more complex and structured and has been added to this document as an update done at M15. The demonstrator focuses on the application of machine learning methods on wine data collected from online social networks of wine passionate users. The dataset analyzed contains: 489,417 wine reviews by 195,678 users, written in 86 languages, related to 51,579 different wines, from 58 wine countries and 2272 wine regions. The predictive analysis conducted on this dataset allows us to show the potential of the machine learning layer of the BDG infrastructure providing efficient and effective methods for assessing the potential market penetration of a given wine in a new country. We estimate this penetration capability by learning a model from user-generated contents about wines in a target country.

¹ <https://www.docker.com/resources/what-container>

² <https://jupyter.org/>

³ <http://kdd.ics.uci.edu/databases/kddcup99/kddcup99.html>

⁴ <https://www.kaggle.com/uciml/red-wine-quality-cortez-et-al-2009>

Section 4 of this document has been added as an update done at M31. The section details the machine learning analytics developed to support the five BigDataGrapes pilots. For each solution we detail: i) the specific task we addressed, ii) a description of the software architecture of the analytics developed, iii) the data acquisition and preprocessing pipeline employed to train and apply the models within the BigDataGrapes infrastructure, iv) the machine-learning techniques that we employ to solve the task, the methodology used and the hyper-parameter tuning performed to provide the best performance to the BigDataGrapes final user. For each technique, we also provide an experimental analysis of the techniques employed against strong baselines and state-of-the-art competitors on the real data provided within the BigDataGrapes consortium. The experimental results reported show the effectiveness of the machine learned analytics developed.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The BigDataGrapes platform aims at providing Predictive Data Analytics tools that go beyond the state-of-the-art for what regards their application to large and complex grapevine-related data assets. Having this ambitious goal in mind, even the first version of the predictive analytics component described in this document has been designed by relying on the core technologies and frameworks for efficient processing of large datasets, e.g., Apache Spark, employed on the lower levels of the BDG platform. Machine learning largely benefits from the distributed execution paradigm that serves as the basis for addressing efficiently the analytics and scalability challenges of grapevines-powered industries.

The document first introduces the main technologies currently used in the first version of the BDG component for performing efficient and scalable analytics over extremely large dataset. The dockerized component provided in this deliverable relies on the BDG software stack discussed in Deliverable 2.3 “BigDataGrapes Software Stack Design” and exploits the distributed execution environment provided by the Persistence and Processing Layers of the BDG architecture contributed in Deliverable 4.1 “Methods and Tools for Scalable Distributed Processing”.

The BDG platform allows the user to learn and apply predictive data analytics over extremely large dataset. We show these functionalities by discussing four demonstrators implemented as Jupyter Notebooks. The first three demonstrators presented in Section 3 deal with different kinds of machine learning tasks: regression, binary classification and multi-label classification. We present the three applications on three different datasets. The first one is synthetically generated while the other two are the KDD CUP 1999 dataset and the Red Wine Quality, both public. We first present how to train several kinds of models addressing the three tasks, i.e., *linear regressors*, *random forest regressors*, *logistic regression classifiers* by interacting with the BDG distributed infrastructure. We then present how to assess the performance of a learned model in terms of a well-known quality metric, i.e., Accuracy. Moreover, we present some basic visualization of the data to provide the user with a useful visual feedback.

Section 3 also presents a fourth demonstrator, which is much more complex and structured. It has been added to this document as an update done at M15 (update 1). The demonstrator focuses on the application of machine learning methods on wine data collected from online social networks of wine passionate users. The dataset analysed contains: 489,417 wine reviews by 195,678 users, written in 86 languages, related to 306,856 different wines, from 57 wine countries and 2,120 wine regions. The predictive analysis conducted on this dataset allows us to show the potential of the machine learning layer of the BDG infrastructure providing efficient and effective methods for assessing the potential market penetration of a given wine on a new country. We estimate this penetration capability by learning a model from user-generated content about wines in the target country.

Section 4 of this document has been added as an update done at M31 (update 2). The section details the machine learning analytics developed to support the five BigDataGrapes pilots. For each solution we detail: i) the specific task we addressed, ii) a description of the software architecture of the analytics developed, iii) the data acquisition and preprocessing pipeline employed to train and apply the models within the BigDataGrapes infrastructure, iv) the machine-learning techniques that we employ to solve the task, the methodology used and the hyper-parameter tuning performed to provide the best performance to the BigDataGrapes final user. For each technique, we also provide an experimental analysis of the techniques employed against strong baselines and state-of-the-art competitors on the real data provided within the BigDataGrapes consortium. The experimental results reported show the effectiveness of the machine learned analytics developed.

This document is organized as follows: Section 2 highlights the main technologies used in the BDG software stack to support and implement scalable predictive analytics. Section 3 describes the design, implementation and application of the BDG predictive analytics component. It also details how to set up and run it on the top of the current version of the BDG platform. Moreover, it discusses the four demonstrators that are provided in the deliverable as running examples showing the functionalities of the BDG platform. Section 4 provides a comprehensive discussion of the machine-learning analytics develop to support the BigDataGrapes pilots. Finally, Section 5 concludes the document.

2 DISTRIBUTED MACHINE LEARNING OVER BIG DATA

In this section, we introduce the main components allowing BigDataGrapes to perform predictive analytics over extremely large dataset. To provide the reader with a self-contained view of the predictive data analytics functionality supported by the first version of the BDG platform, we first introduce Apache Spark, a scalable big data processing framework that is the de-facto technological state-of-the-art for parallel and distributed batch computations, and Apache HDFS, a distributed file system enabling persistence of information. We finally introduce MLLib, the machine learning library working on Apache Spark that allows distributed and parallel learning from big data of effective models for regression and classification tasks.

2.1 APACHE SPARK

Apache Spark (<https://spark.apache.org/>) is a well-known and open-source framework for big data processing. It has been designed at the University of California, Berkeley's AMPLab in 2009. Later, the Spark project moved to the Apache Software Foundation, which has maintained it since 2010. As previous big data processing frameworks, Spark provides an interface for programming clusters with implicit data parallelism and fault tolerance. The novel key feature that motivates its success and popularity is the introduction of the “Resiliend Distributed Dataset” (RDD), a data structure implementing a read-only multiset of data items distributed over a cluster of machines and guaranteeing fault-tolerance. The introduction of the RDD was needed in response to the limitations of the MapReduce cluster computing paradigm, which forces a particular linear dataflow structure on distributed programs. With MapReduce, programs simply read input data from disk, map a function across the data, reduce the results of the map, and store reduction results on the file system. The functions of the RDD in Spark allows distributed programs to interact with a (deliberately) restricted form of distributed shared memory. This novel approach allows Spark to ease the implementation of both iterative algorithms, that visit the data multiple times in a loop, and interactive/exploratory data analysis, i.e., the repeated database-style querying of data. As a consequence, the latency of this kind of applications is extremely reduced, i.e., by several orders of magnitude compared to a MapReduce implementation (as was common in Apache Hadoop stacks).

2.2 APACHE HDFS

The Apache Hadoop software library (<http://hadoop.apache.org/>) is a framework supporting the distributed processing of large datasets across clusters of computers using simple programming models. It is designed to scale out from single servers to thousands of machines, each offering local computation and storage. Among the Apache Hadoop's core components, there is the Hadoop File System (HDFS). HDFS or Hadoop File System is the file system in which the data is stored. The stored data may be structured, semi-structured or unstructured thus containing for example either the tables of a relational database, or a set of json or log files. HDFS is designed for massive scalability, it stores unlimited amounts of data in a single platform. As the data grow, it is possible to simply add more servers to scale linearly. Furthermore, a key feature of HDFS is reliability. It automatically performs multiple copies of the data stored, letting it always available for access and protection from data loss. Built-in fault tolerance means servers can fail but a system will remain available for all workloads.

2.3 MLLIB

MLlib (<https://spark.apache.org/mllib/>) is the machine learning library for Apache Spark. It is a fully-fledged tool containing many algorithms and utilities for several tasks ranging from classification (logistic regression, naive Bayes, etc.) to regression (generalized linear regression, survival regression, isolation regression, etc.) and gradient-boosted algorithms based on trees, e.g., random forests, multiple additive regression trees. It also provides distributed methods for clustering (K-means, Gaussian mixtures (GMMs), etc.) and for mining frequent itemsets, association rules, and sequential patterns. MLLib also provides utilities for data pre-processing exploiting the underlying distributed Spark environment. Pre-processing of data includes feature

transformations (standardization, normalization, hashing) and easy statistics on data (summaries, hypothesis testing, etc). All this processing blocks can be also combined together toward the definition of a “Pipeline” of machine learning techniques that enable model evaluation and efficient hyper-parameter tuning. The persistence of the results is also implemented by the definition of methods for saving and loading models and pipelines to/from the file system.

2.4 H2O SPARKING WATER

Sparkling Water (<https://www.h2o.ai/products/h2o-sparkling-water/>) allows users to combine the fast, scalable machine learning algorithms of H2O with the capabilities of Apache Spark. Sparkling Water stems from H2O, an in-memory platform for machine learning, the potential of performing effective and efficient machine learning on big data. Sparkling Water and Apache Spark allows for a seamless experience for users who want to interact with distributed databases/filesystems, build a model and make predictions, and then use the results again in Apache Spark. It is used for exploring and analysing datasets held in cloud computing systems and in the Apache HDFS as well as in the conventional operating-systems Linux, macOS, and Microsoft Windows. The H2O software is written in Java, Python, and R. Its graphical-user interface is compatible with four browsers: Chrome, Safari, Firefox, and Internet Explorer.

3 BIGDATAGRAPES PREDICTIVE DATA ANALYTICS SETUP

The BDG platform relies on MLLib, the Apache HDFS file system and Apache Spark to allow the BDG users to develop methods for predictive data analytics, i.e., classification, regression, and clustering algorithms, and to interact and use them on the BDG distributed infrastructure. In the following sections we detail how to setup and install the BDG Predictive Data Analytics component and how to run the toy demonstrators provided in the first version of the deliverable. Demonstrators are implemented in Python as Jupyter Notebooks (<http://jupyter.org/>).

3.1 REQUIREMENTS

The Predictive Big Data Analytics functionality of the BDG platform is available after setting up the BDG architecture as detailed in D4.1. Interested users should refer to D4.1 and follow all the steps reported in Section 3 to setup a working BDG architecture.

3.2 DOCKER COMPONENTS SCHEMA

Figure 1 shows the components used by the Predictive Data Analytics functionality of BDG and their implementation as Docker components. In the Figure we made transparent all the components of the BDG architecture not explicitly needed by this functionality. As detailed above, the Predictive Data Analytics functionality relies on MLLib, Spark and HDFS to perform machine learning tasks over extremely large datasets. We also report the addresses and ports used by these containers. Particularly, the Spark component is composed of one master node/container and many workers nodes/containers linked to the master. Similarly, the HDFS component has one *namenode* container and many *datanodes* containers.

Figure 1: BigDataGrapes Components used by the Predictive Data Analytics functionality and their mapping on Docker Containers.

3.3 HOW TO GET THE CODE

To get the code demonstrating the Predictive Data Analytics functionality of BDG, clone the following GitHub repository

```
$ git clone https://github.com/BigDataGrapes-EU/deliverable-D4.3.git
```

The repository contains three Jupyter Notebooks and a Bash shell script that should be used to initialize the Big Data Grapes Platform. The script should be executed after cloning the repository by running the Bash command below:

```
$ ./run-components.sh
```

The Bash script above downloads the Docker images and builds the environment according to the predefined configuration settings. The Bash script also starts the Docker containers of the BigDataGrapes software stack components.

Finally, to execute the demonstrators, run the following Bash command:

```
$ ./run-jupyter_notebooks.sh
```

The Bash script above starts the Jupyter notebooks for predictive data analytics using the BigDataGrapes platform.

3.4 DESCRIPTION OF THE DEMONSTRATORS

The Predictive Data Analytics demonstrator consists of Python code made available in three Jupyter Notebook files. The first one shows how to train linear and random forest regressors with MLLib on synthetic data. The second one details how to perform a classification task with MLLib on a real-world public dataset, the KDD Cup 1999 challenge. The third one shows how to train multi-label classifiers with MLLib on the Red Wine Quality Dataset.

Jupyter Notebook (<http://jupyter.org/>) is an open-source Web application that allows the user to create and share documents that contain live code, equations, visualizations and narrative text. They are extremely useful for data cleaning and transformation, numerical simulation, statistical modeling, data visualization, machine learning, and much more. The Notebook supports over 40 programming languages. Code inside a notebook can produce rich, interactive output. More importantly, Jupyter Notebook can exploit big data tools, such as Apache Spark, from Python, R and Scala.

Figure 2 shows a snapshot of one of the Jupyter Notebooks of the demo. A Jupyter Notebook is a sequence of cells containing code, text, images, etc. The execution of each cell allows to run the code inside it. The output of each cell is then shown in the notebook so to allow easy interaction with the user.

H2020 RIA BigDataGrapes - Predictive Data Analytics (T4.3)

This deliverable (D4.3) presents how to train machine learning models with the BigDataGrapes distributed processing architecture. In particular, we present how to train classifiers with MLLib (<https://spark.apache.org/ml/lib/>).


```
In [1]: from pyspark import SparkContext
```

```
In [2]: import math
import urllib
import random
import numpy as np
import pydoop.hdfs as hdfs

from numpy import array
from pyspark.mllib.regression import LabeledPoint
```

```
In [3]: %matplotlib inline
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

Connection to the BDG Apache Spark

```
In [4]: # standalone mode below
#sc = SparkContext(appName="Classification-WineDataset", master="master[*]")

# distributed mode below
sc = SparkContext(appName="Classification-WineDataset", master="spark://spark-master:7077")

# setting logger level
sc.setLogLevel("ERROR")
```

Figure 2: Snapshot of a Jupyter Notebook taken from the Predictive Data Analytics demonstrator.

The three demonstrators of the Predictive Data Analytics functionality of BDG are both structured around four different steps that are detailed in the following.

3.4.1 Connection to the BDG Apache Spark enabling distributed computation

This is a preliminary operations allowing Jupyter Notebook to connect to the Spark context used for the computation, i.e., the master node that manage the distributed computation on the cluster. Data generation/download for the regression/classification demonstrators works as follows:

- In the regression demonstrator we generate synthetic data and we preliminary plot them to allow the user to understand their shape and complexity.
- The binary classification demonstrator exploits real data from a well-known data challenge: KDD Cup 1999. The dataset is used for the Third International Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining Tools Competition, which was held in conjunction with KDD-99 The Fifth International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining. The competition task was to build a network intrusion detector, a predictive model capable of distinguishing between “bad” connections, called intrusions or attacks, and “good” normal connections. This database contains a standard set of data to be audited, which includes a wide variety of intrusions simulated in a military network environment. The demonstrator shows how to build a Logistic Regression Classifier with MLLib. We also show how to interact with the BDG HDFS distributed file system by downloading and storing the dataset on HDFS.
- The multi-label classification demonstrator is built around the Red Wine Quality Dataset made available on Kaggle (<https://www.kaggle.com/piyushgoyal443/red-wine-dataset/discussion>). The dataset is related to red variants of the Portuguese "Vinho Verde" wine. Due to privacy and logistic issues, only physicochemical (inputs) and sensory (the output) variables are available (e.g., there is no data about

grape types, wine brand, wine selling price, etc.). The dataset is made up of 1599 instances. Each instance has 11 attributes and one label, i.e., the quality of the wine produced expressed on a ten-grade scale, i.e., {1, 2, ..., 10}. The classes are ordered and not balanced.

3.4.2 Reading of the data with Apache Spark (to create a Resilient Distributed Dataset (RDD))

The three demonstrators read the datasets used in two different ways. While the regression demonstrator shows how to build Spark RDDs from NumPy arrays the second and the third one, i.e., the ones dealing with classification read data from HDFS showing an example of interaction with the BDG distributed file system.

3.4.3 Training three different kinds of machine learning applications with MLLib

- Regression (Linear and Random Forest Regressors): We intentionally generate data by perturbing results from linear, square, and sine functions with gaussian noise. The visualization of the results of the regression clearly show that the three lines fitted follow the shape of the data used to fit them. Indeed, this kind of regressors are very simple yet not totally able to deal with the complexity of square and sine data (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Application of three linear regression models (red, green and blue solid lines) trained on synthetic data generated by perturbing linear, square and sine functions with gaussian noise.

- We then add a more complex (non-linear) regressor, i.e., random forest, to deal with the complexity of the data. The prediction produced is now more accurate as Figure 4 shows.

Figure 4: Application of three random forest regressors (red, green and blue solid lines) trained on synthetic data generated by perturbing linear, square and sine functions with gaussian noise.

- Binary Classification (Logistic Regression Classifier):** In the binary classification demonstrator we train a binary classifier by employing logistic regression. The demonstrator is built around the KDD 1999 dataset that comes split in train/test. Train and test data are read from HDFS to allow Apache Spark to build two RDDs that are then used to build the classifier. We first build the classifier on training data. We then perform an evaluation step by computing the accuracy metric, i.e., the proportion of true results (both true positives and true negatives) among the total number of cases examined, on the test set of the dataset. This information is then returned to the used to allow an easy comparison of the performance with other classifiers.
- Multi-label Classification (Logistic Regression Classifier):** In the multi-label classification demonstrator we train a multi label classifier by employing logistic regression. The demonstrator is built around the Red Wine Quality Dataset that we split in train/test. The dataset is made up of examples labeled with a “quality” label expressed on a ten-grade scale. We thus learn a classifier to guess the correct class, i.e., quality of each wine. We learn the classifier after loading data from HDFS. We then perform an evaluation step by computing the accuracy metric, i.e., the proportion of true results (both true positives and true negatives) among the total number of cases examined, on the test set of the dataset. This information is then returned to the used to allow an easy comparison of the performance with other classifiers.

3.4.4 Disconnection from the BDG Apache Spark environment

This is the last, yet very important, phase needed to disconnect the Jupyter Notebook from the BDG big data platform. The operation allows for freeing the resources allocated and used by the computation. Each step above is documented inside the Jupyter Notebooks. We clearly identify each part by adding a textual cell describing when a specific step starts. We also add several cells allowing for visualizing the dataset and the intermediate results.

3.5 ASSESSMENT ON ONLINE WINE DATA

This section discusses the updates of this deliverable added at M15. The aim of this update is to assess on a large scale the machine learning methods for predictive data analytics provided on top of the BDG infrastructure. Specifically, we present the results of an investigation focusing on the application of machine learning methods on wine data collected from online social networks of wine passionate users. The data available consist of a general description of the wine (wine name, producer, year of production, wine grape varieties, etc.), user-generated content associated with it (user ratings and reviews), and user information (unique Id, nationality,

etc.). The dataset used contains: 489,417 wine reviews by 195,678 users, written in 86 languages, related to 51,579 different wines, from 58 wine countries and 2272 wine regions.

The predictive analysis conducted on this dataset allows us to show the potential of the machine learning layer of the BDG infrastructure exploited in this case for descriptive analytics and for deploying efficient and effective methods for assessing the potential market penetration of a given wine in a new country. We estimate this penetration capability by learning a model from user-generated contents for estimating wine ratings in a target country from wine characteristics. In details, the investigation conducted aims at answering the four main research questions:

1. Is it possible to derive “aroma fingerprints” of a wine from user-generated content?
2. Is it possible to derive “taste fingerprints” of a wine from user-generated content?
3. Is it possible to exploit the fingerprints above to assess how wines are perceived in a specific country? Is there any similarity between countries in the way they perceive a specific wine?
4. Is it possible to build machine learning models that predict the user rating of a wine given its aromas and taste fingerprint?

3.5.1 Preliminary investigation of the data

We first perform a preliminary analysis of the data available. To this end, Table 1 shows the number of reviews in the dataset after data cleaning grouped by language.

Table 1: Distribution of wine reviews by language.

Language	# Reviews
EN	357,347
FR	17,166
PT	13,007
IT	10,949
DE	8,388

We note that English is the most popular language. We thus focus our analysis on the reviews written in English. We now detail the reviews above by user country and plot the distribution obtained in the Figure below.

Figure 5: Distribution of wine reviews by country.

We observe that the countries with the highest number of reviews are US and GB. Netherland, Canada and Australia also contribute significantly. The distribution of reviews per country is highly skewed. We observe that non-English-speaking countries contribute with a significant number of reviews to the total even if the number of English reviews is larger than the sum of all the remaining non-English reviews. Figure 5 plots the distribution per user country of the reviews written in English.

Another interesting analysis regards the distribution of the wine rating that is expressed on a nine-graded scale from one to five, where one means “very bad” while five means “excellent”. We plot the distribution of the user ratings to understand what are the most popular classes. The figure below shows the number of reviews (Y axis) per rating value (X axis).

Figure 6: Distribution of wine ratings by score value.

We observe that the most popular classes are 3, 3.5, 4. These three classes cover together up to 270K reviews consisting in the majority of the reviews present in the dataset. We also observe that wines in the dataset are provided with an aggregation by wine grapes, i.e., wines are grouped together using the grape that characterizes them the most. We call this aggregation “wine type”. We observe that the first four wine types are: cabernet-sauvignon, chardonnay, merlot, pinot-noir, sauvignon blanc. This aggregation of wines by wine grape allows us to perform the analysis we present in the next section.

3.5.2 Building aromas fingerprints of a wine from user-generated content

We now show how to exploit user reviews to build an aroma profile of a wine. To this end we select from our dataset the user reviews written in English. The generation of the aroma profile is done by identifying in the text of the reviews the occurrences of terms belonging to a taxonomy of wine aromas provided by one of the most popular social networks of wine lovers.

By using the user reviews, we build a multi-dimensional fingerprint of aromas perceived as characterizing a specific wine group on the basis of the user country. Each dimension of the fingerprint measures the presence of a specific aroma in the reviews of each group of wines. It is thus a term frequency vector where each element of the vector is the frequency of a specific aroma in the user reviews. After a normalization process, the per-country multi-dimensional vectors enable interesting similarity operations thus measuring the perception of the same wine type in different countries.

In the following figures, i.e., Figure 7 and Figure 8, we show as examples the fingerprints of the most popular wine group, i.e., cabernet-sauvignon. The top half of Figure 7 and Figure 8 present a heat-map of the vectors built for the top five most-popular countries (US, GB, NL, AU and CA). On the X-axis we report the different aromas taken from the taxonomy described before. The heat-map plots the frequency of each aroma in the user reviews of each specific country. The US is the country with the highest number of reviews showing also the highest variance in terms of aromas. On the contrary, GB, i.e., the second most popular country shows a narrow set of well-perceived aromas with a long tail of low-frequency aromas. The same consideration holds also for Canada and Australia, while the Netherlands and Denmark show a more selective fingerprint with no tail of low-frequency aromas.

The bottom half of Figure 7 and Figure 8 present a heat map showing the similarity between countries computed starting from the vectors above for cabernet-sauvignon. The heat map visually shows how similarly cabernet sauvignon is perceived in different countries. The similarity is computed using the cosine distance. Interestingly, USA, Australia and Canada perceive cabernet sauvignon in a very similar way (similarity > 0.6). Indeed, the similarity between Canada and USA is even stronger (similarity > 0.8). On the contrary, the Netherlands has a different perception of this kind of wine as its similarity with all other English-speaking countries (USA, Canada, Australia, Great Britain) is always lower than 0.2. In terms of specific aromas, users from Canada and USA identify the presence of cherry in the cabernet sauvignon-based wines while users from Australia and Great Britain identify the prevalence of oak. Instead, users from the Netherlands report the presence of fruit/red fruits aromas. The software shared in the GitHub repository of the project (details in Section 3.3) proposes the same analysis for the five biggest wine groups, i.e., cabernet-sauvignon, chardonnay, merlot, pinot-noir, sauvignon-blanc. For each one we provide the two heat maps, the first one visualizing the aromas fingerprints per country while the second one visualizing the similarity between countries.

Country Similarity (Aromas on cabernet-sauvignon)

Figure 7: Aroma fingerprints perceived for cabernet-sauvignon by country and their similarities.

3.5.3 Building tastes fingerprints of a wine from user-generated content

We apply the same methodology described in Section 3.5.2 to derive a “tastes fingerprint” of a wine from user-generated content. In this case we used the taxonomy of wine tastes available here: <https://winefolly.com/tutorial/wine-aroma-wheel-100-flavors/>. As before, we report the results for the largest wine group, i.e., cabernet sauvignon in Figure 8. The analysis confirms the results presented before for aromas. USA shows a very high similarity with Canada (similarity > 0.8) while it is also similar with Australia (similarity > 0.6). The Netherland has its own way of perceiving cabernet sauvignon while Great Britain shows slight similarities with Canada and the Netherland (similarity > 0.5). In terms of tastes, English-speaking countries

(USA, GB, Australia and Canada) identify smoothness in cabernet sauvignon while GB and the Netherlands frequently report its fruity characteristics.

Country Similarity (Tastes on cabernet-sauvignon)

Figure 8: Taste fingerprints perceived for cabernet-sauvignon by country and their similarities.

The analysis presented in Sections 3.5.2 and 3.5.3 answer the first three research question: we derive a way to synthesize aromas and tastes fingerprints from wine user reviews. The fingerprints are based on a public taxonomy of aromas from domain experts. We also show how to understand the per-country perception of a wine by exploiting these fingerprints. The fingerprints allow to identify the most important aromas that users from a given country identify in a wine. We believe this is an interesting tool for wine makers that allow them to better target their products for specific markets. In addition, the proposed fingerprints built from user-

generated content can also be exploited to compute the similarity of perception of users of different countries thus allowing to better understand the market.

3.5.4 Machine Learning for User Rating Prediction

We now present the application of supervised machine learning techniques to the data. We apply machine learning to build a user rating predictor, i.e., predict the rating of a wine in a given country. We focus this analysis on user reviews from the USA. We exploit the BDG platform to learn three different kind of predictors, i.e., Decision Trees, Random Forest and Gradient Boosted Trees regressors. We also employ two different feature representation of the wine:

1. We first employ the metadata of each wine collected from online social networks, i.e., user country, wine country, name of the wine region, year of the wine, wine alcohol, wine acidity, wine body, wine grapes.
2. We include in the above representation the TF-IDF representation of user reviews, i.e., we add the user feedback expressed in terms of reviews.

The three models are optimized by using grid search with a standard three-fold validation methodology. The software provided on GitHub details how to learn the three regressors by using the BDG platform. Figure 9 shows the performance in terms of RMSE of the three models each one trained with the two different feature sets. The best prediction performance in predicting the user rating is achieved by the Gradient Boosted Trees model. The exploitation of the user reviews in the feature set (GBT-TFIDF) allows this predictor to achieve an RMSE of 0.553. On the contrary, the Decision Tree predictor is the worst performing predictor with a performance that is up to 6% worse than the one provided by GBT-TFIDF. Indeed, the decision tree regressor is not able to exploit the user reviews as the performance achieved by DT-TFIDF (0.588) is almost the same the one obtained by the plain DT (0.59). Random Forest shows a similar behavior even if the performance of the two predictors is better than the one obtained by Decision Tree regressors.

Figure 9: RMSE of the various predictors on wine rating estimation.

This section shows that the BDG infrastructure allows to run state-of-the-art machine learning methods to build user rating predictors. We present two different feature sets derived from our data and show that the exploitation of the user reviews as features for wines allows to improve the predictive power of the models. Specifically, one of them, Gradient Boosted Trees predictor, shows a good improvement (up to 4.9%) when exploiting textual information from reviews. We conclude this section by presenting an analysis of the feature

importance, i.e., what predictive power are the features providing for the model. As before, this analysis is done on the two feature sets by training a random forest with a maximum depth equal to 15 and number of trees equal to 15. The analysis performed on the first feature set, i.e., the one not exploiting the review text, (Figure 10) identifies that two out of the three most important features for predicting the rating of a wine for the US users are: the name of the region and the country where the wine is produced. This means that the provenience of the wine is an important signal to consider when predicting the rating of a wine. The second and, from the fifth feature on, all features belong to characteristics of the wine itself, i.e., acidity, alcoholic degree, body, composition in terms of grapes, and year of production. This is an expected result as these are all important dimensions to consider when reviewing a wine. Another important feature highlighted by this analysis regards the list of foods to pair with the wine (the fourth most important feature) meaning that users evaluate also this aspect when expressing their rating. From Figure 9, we learn that user reviews are important to better focus the user rating prediction. We then evaluate the importance of the features when employing the second feature set, i.e., the one combining user reviews with the metadata of each wine.

Figure 10: Feature importance for the first feature set.

The feature importance of the second feature set used is shown in Figure 11. Here we observe a swap in the feature importance. The first most important feature is, in fact, the country where the wine is produced followed by the region of the wine. This confirms that geographical information of the wine are important signals in determining the prediction of the user rating. Differently from before, the fourth most important feature used by the model here is the TF-IDF weight of the terms composing the review. This behavior confirms what has been observed before (Figure 9), i.e., user reviews are a significant source of information for predicting the user rating of a wine. Some features characterizing the nature of the specific wine, i.e., acidity, style, and the foods to pair with are also present here confirming their importance in determining the prediction.

Figure 11: Feature importance for the second feature set.

This investigation is an answer to the fourth research question: it is possible to exploit online wine data (both metadata and user reviews) to build effective predictors of the user rating. Experiments show that the exploitation of user reviews allows for a better prediction model. Indeed, this investigation confirms the validity of the BDG platform to learn predictive analytics effectively over large and heterogeneous datasets.

3.6 HOW TO RUN THE CODE

To run the demonstrators, after following the instructions detailed in Section 3.3, the user should point her browser to the following Jupyter Notebook URL: http://<server_address>:9999

The password used to protect the Jupyter Notebook instance is “bigdatagrapes”.

After a successful login the user can open the files below:

- D4.3-PredictiveDataAnalyticsWithMLlib-Regression-Py2.ipynb
- D4.3-PredictiveDataAnalyticsWithMLlib-Classification-Py2-KDDCUP1999.ipynb
- D4.3-PredictiveDataAnalyticsWithMLlib-MultiLabelClassification-Py2-WineDataset.ipynb
- D4.3-WineDataAnalysis-FlavorsTastes-PredictionUserRating.ipynb

The execution of the code can be done by running each cell from the beginning to the end of each notebook and wait for the result.

4 MACHINE LEARNING ANALYTICS FOR THE BIGDATAGRAPES PILOTS

In this section, we detail the updates of this deliverable added at M30. We describe the machine-learning analytics developed to serve the needs of the five BigDataGrapes pilots, namely i) Table and Wine Grapes, ii) Wine Quality, iii) Farm Management, iv) Natural Cosmetics, and v) Food Protection pilots. In the following, we provide a per-pilot overview of the analytics with an analysis of their effectiveness on real BDG data. As before, demonstrators are implemented in Python as Jupyter Notebooks (<http://jupyter.org/>). For each pilot, Rest APIs have been developed and integrated within the BDG platform.

4.1 TABLE AND WINE GRAPES PILOT

Soil properties, climate conditions and cultivation techniques constitute significant variables, which affect the quality of the final product. In particular, soil data (soil texture, soil electrical conductivity etc.) and weather data (average temperature, humidity etc.) affect both crop quality data (sugar content, anthocyanins content, phenolic compounds concentrations etc.) and crop quantity data (crop yield, berry weight and size etc.). The goal of this pilot is to allow the user to explore and visualize the correlations in the sensor and phenological farming data collected in all test sites located in Greece to understand and explain what affects grape quality and yield. Data intelligence is used to answer questions on how some attributes, such as soil properties, affect grape quality and yield. Data integration has been achieved by using semantic web and ontologies in order to have all data connected in a knowledge graph.

4.1.1 Software Architecture

For this pilot, we have designed and developed the software architecture shown in Figure 12. The architecture is mainly composed of three components: Data Layer, Analytic API and the Decision Support Interface. At the Data Layer component, we find the data parsers and crawlers which are in charge of collecting and properly structuring the data for the further analytic tasks. The Analytic API performs associations and correlations between precision agriculture information (sensor data layer), phenological data and grape chemical analysis (lab data) and satellite imagery indexes (satellite data layer). The correlation analysis can then be queried providing correlation analysis insights that will help decision support systems.

Figure 12: Pilot 1, Software Architecture.

All components have been developed using python version 3. Specifically, the data parsers for the data and sensor data use the pandas python library (pandas.pydata.org) to load csv and Excel files content, while the crawlers for consuming satellite Imagery data from the Geocledian API (geocledian.com/agknow/api/v3/) use

the python library requests (requests.readthedocs.io/). To compute the Pearson correlation coefficient the Analytic API uses numpy (numpy.org/) for efficient processing. For a quick visualization of the heatmaps with the correlation values, we employ the seaborn library (seaborn.pydata.org/) on top of python notebooks.

4.1.2 Table and Wine Grapes data

Measurements related to the Table Grapes pilot take place during the whole duration of the project. Emphasis is given in the summer months, May through September, while grapevines grow and produce grapes.

The boundaries of the vineyards were geo-referenced using GPS technology at the very beginning of the project, as soon as the experimental fields were chosen. Time-stable zones were formed using soil electrical conductivity (ECa) mapping, assisted by elevation mapping using the RTK-GPS. Soil, weather and farming data has been continuously collected, starting on Day 1 of the project. Canopy characteristics and vegetation indices have been recorded with the use of Crop Circle and SpectroSense2 sensors six times per season/summer starting at the beginning/middle of May, so that the phenological development of the grapevine, which is divided into 9 principal growth stages, will be followed in the best way. These measurements have been repeated every year. Some of the qualitative and quantitative characters of the grapevines, such as pH, soluble solids, total titratable acidity, antioxidant capacity by DPPH, FRAP assay, and amino acids, were tested three times over a season. Finally, the rest of the qualitative and quantitative characters were assessed at the end of each season, when harvesting. Similarly, yield mapping was also estimated once per year.

First of all, let us recall the “three layers” where we collect data for this pilot. The datasets recorded for the BigDataGrapes project through this pilot are the following:

- Ground (location-specific) data – using sensors to record information for the plants and the environment they are in. They include:
 - Remote sensing for spatial data, topographical and elevation mapping
 - Identification of grapevine varieties
 - Geo-referenced apparent soil electrical conductivity (ECa)
 - Canopy characteristics and vegetation indices
 - Yield mapping
 - Soil, weather and farming data
- Lab data - laboratory analysis to get information from the inside of the plants. They include:
 - Qualitative and quantitative characteristics; Grape and berry mechanical properties (weight, length, width, density etc.), berry deformation, berry detachment, density, grape volume, berries diameter, berries weight
 - For wine and table grapes: soluble solids, pH, total titratable acidity, total phenols and anthocyanins, total flavonoid content, total flavanol, flavonol, flavone content, tannins, antioxidant capacity (trans-resveratrol, piceid, ϵ -viniferin) by DPPH, FRAP assay, amino acids.
 - Full phenolic profile of grapevine varieties in correlation with the phenological stages to improve the quality of viticultural products
 - For table grapes: leaf analysis, foliar chlorophyll contents photosynthetic pigment content of the leaves, water potential correlated to the proline content
- Airborne data (satellite imagery) – Sentinel-2 and Landsat 7 satellite imagery vegetation indexes:
 - **NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index)**. Quantifies vegetation by measuring the difference between near-infrared (which vegetation strongly reflects) and red light (which vegetation absorbs). Overall, NDVI is a standardized way to measure healthy vegetation. When you have high NDVI values, you have healthier vegetation. When you have low NDVI, you have less or no vegetation.

- **NDRE1 (Normalized Difference Red Edge Index (v1))**. Substitution of NDVI’s red band with NDRE’s red edge band provides a measurement that is not as strongly absorbed by just the topmost layers of leaves.
- **NDRE2 (Normalized Difference Red Edge Index (v2))**. Substitution of NDVI’s red band with NDRE’s red edge band (700nm).
- **NDWI (Normalized Difference Water Index)**. NDWI is less susceptible to atmospheric scattering than NDVI, but does not completely remove the background soil reflectance effects, similar to NDVI.
- **SAVI (Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index)**. The index is a transformation technique that minimizes soil brightness influences from spectral vegetation indices involving red and near-infrared (NIR) wavelengths.
- **EVI2 (Enhanced Vegetation Index 2)**. The enhanced vegetation index (EVI) is an optimized vegetation index designed to enhance the vegetation signal with improved sensitivity in high biomass regions and improved vegetation monitoring through a de-coupling of the canopy background signal and a reduction in atmosphere influences.
- **CI-RE (Chlorophyll Index - Red Edge)**. The chlorophyll index is used to calculate the total chlorophyll content of the leaves. The Cgreen and Cired-edge values are sensitive to small variations in the chlorophyll content and consistent across most species.

4.1.3 Correlation analysis on Table and Wine Grapes data

We used the Palivou Mesi field as a study case for the correlation analysis between the three data layers. Palivou Estate is located in Nemea, planted with *Vitis vinifera* L. cv. “Agiorgitiko” and “Merlot” for winemaking. The row orientation is northeast-southwest, and the training/trellis system is VSP (vertical shoot positioned)- cane pruning, double Guyot. For the pre-processing of the data collected from the field, we have split the area of the field into 100 cells of equals size as shown in Figure 13. The idea is that we can collect insights of how these properties collected from different sources correlated between them for the same field. Then, we represent the property of the field as a vector with $C \times T$, where C is the number of cells and T is the number of temporal points considered for the analysis. Since most of the data have been collected from the last two year (2018 and 2019), for most of the analysis reported in this document we have T equals 2. We have used Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients to perform the correlation analysis.

Figure 13: Split of Palivou Mesi field into 100 cells.

Currently, the Analytic API manages three scenarios for the correlation analysis involving the three layers of data for this pilot:

The API resource *sensorvslab* handles associations and correlations between precision agriculture information (sensor data) and phenological data and grape chemical analysis (lab data). For the sensor data, we have specifically investigated the following properties: Soil Electrical Conductivity (CV1m) and Elevation. For the lab data layer, we took the Sugar content (Brix%), # of Grape Crates per cells, Titratable acidity (%), Mass of Harvest Product (kg) for the correlation analysis. As shown in Figure 14, for the year 2019, the highest correlation between the lab data layer (y-axis) and sensor data was seen for the properties *Elevation* and *# of Grape Crates per Cell* with Pearson coefficient equals to 0.307. The experiment also shows a low negative correlation of -0.208 between the properties *Sugar Content* and *Elevation*.

Figure 14: Heatmap visualization of the insights provided by the API resource: *sensorvslab*.

The API resource *sensorvssatellite* correlates the sensor data with earth observation data on vegetation indexes (NDVI) for similar dates. In this scenario, we use the RED, REDi, NIR, NIRi, NIRr, NDVI and LAI of the ground Sensors records from the top of the canopies to correlate with the Vegetation indexes computed from the satellite imagery. Figure 15 shows the correlation coefficient results for the years of 2018 and 2019, with the ground sensor data and the satellite imagery indicated in the axis-y and axis-x, respectively. Clearly the NIR exhibits a positive correlation with all the satellite imagery properties, whereas the NIRi has shown a negative correlation for all of them.

Figure 15: Heatmap visualization of the insights provided by the API resource: *sensorvssatellite*.

The API resource *labvssatellite* correlates lab data with earth observation data from satellite imagery. At the third scenario of our analysis, we have considered again the data lab with Yield and Quality properties (e.g., Sugar content (Brix%), # of Grape Crates per cells, Titratable acidity (%), Mass of Harvest Product (kg)), and the satellite imagery properties. Figure 16 shows for the year 2019 the results of our correlation analysis for this scenario. The results propose a relevant negative correlation between the Sugar Content (Brix %) and all the other vegetation indexes derived from the satellite imagery observation.

Figure 16: Heatmap visualization of the insights provided by the API resource: *labvssatellite*.

4.2 WINE MAKING PILOT

The wine making pilot studies the viticulture and the ecophysiology of the vine to achieve a better knowledge and better control of grape quality. In details, the goal of the pilot is to study: i) enology with, as major research axes, the expression of quality potential existing in the grapes and wines and the on-line monitoring and control of the alcoholic fermentation, ii) technological processes aiming to propose and study innovative technologies applicable to various steps of winemaking, iii) the valuation of coproducts, extraction of molecules and environmental impacts.

In this pilot, we study an application of machine learning techniques (deep neural network) for the estimation of the number of leaves of the vine. The number of leaves is a key indicator of vegetative organogenesis in grapevine. Leaf emission rate (or vegetative organogenesis rhythm) depends on the variety and can be impacted by the environment (water availability in the soil, air temperature, air humidity, radiation).

There are several uses of a timely and detailed information about the number of leaves such as:

- modeling organogenesis in grapevine and improving existing models of leaf emission rate as a function of time or thermal time.
- characterizing genetic diversity of leaf emission rate is a major issue to better understand the existing variability (which could be used to adapt variety choices to local climate) and its genetic control (region of the genome – QTL or genes).
- in genetic studies which simultaneously study thousands of plants, such as the LEPSE experiments carried out into the PhenoArch phenotyping platform, knowing the development stage (leaf number) of all plants on a given day is essential to avoid bias in the measurement of other variables. For example, if transpiration of the whole progeny is measured, ideally it must be done at a similar developmental stage for all plants.

However, counting leaves of thousands of plants is a laborious and time-consuming task, which is hard to manage in parallel with other measurements. The main objective of this pilot is thus to develop a machine-learning pipeline aiming at counting leaves from side-view grapevine images taken into the imaging cabin of the PhenoArch platform (see Figure 18) managed by INRA.

4.2.1 Software Architecture

For this pilot, we have designed and developed the software architecture shown in Figure 17. The architecture is mainly composed of three components: Data Layer, Rest API and the Decision Support Interface. At the Data Layer component, we find the data integration steps needed to handle the plant image and its related metadata. The Analytic API performs the leaf count prediction from plant image and metadata. The Analytic API can then be queried to provide an estimation of the leaf count given an image and its metadata to the final user.

Figure 17: Pilot 2, Software Architecture.

All components have been developed using python version 3. Specifically, the data preprocessors use the pandas python library (pandas.pydata.org) to load csv and the python Keras library (<https://keras.io/>). The deep learning models have been implemented with Keras.

4.2.2 Deep Learning for Counting Leaves

The PhenoArch phenotyping platform ran two experimentations, one in 2012 and another in 2013, collecting two datasets of plant images. For each of the two experimentations, it took pictures of plants every two following days (sometimes the gap can be higher).

Figure 18: Photos of a grapevine from the PhenoArch phenotyping platform. Top, 0 and 90° views.

For each plant and day of imaging, in the 2012 dataset, three images are usually taken per plant, one top view and two side views, 0 and 90° views. An example of plant shot in 2012 is reported in Figure 18. In the 2013 dataset instead, 13 images are usually taken per plant (one top view and twelve side views, one each 30 degrees 0 to 330°). The different angles are identified by the “cameraAngle” field in the JSON data. Cameras are always fixed during one experiment, adopting the same position and settings. The plant rotates using a brushless motor (to

mimic a turning table), so each side image is taken always in the same directions for each. On a regular basis, plants are analyzed by experts that annotate the number of leaves of each plant. The annotation frequency is lower than the imaging, and even the dates do not correspond. To this end, in order to create a proper dataset to be used in a machine learning application, the ground truth label (number of leaves of each image) has been inferred using a leaf progression model. Leaf progression is a process highly driven by temperature. A linear model of leaf number vs thermal time yields very good results. Table 2 provides a brief description of the main characteristics of the two datasets, while Figure 19 shows the distributions of the number of leaves in the two datasets.

Table 2: Description of the two grapevine image datasets gathered by the PhenoArch phenotyping platform.

Dataset	ARCH2012-03-14	ARCH2013-03-17
# Images (with top view)	81363	179093
# Images (without top view)	54242	165112
# Plants	26265	13676

Figure 19: Distributions of the number of leaves in the two grapevine image datasets.

The machine learning solution adopted for the counting leaves pipeline exploits state-of-the-art deep learning techniques based on artificial neural networks to infer the number of leaves from each side-view grapevine image. In details, a combination of Convolutional and Feedforward neural network layers is employed to solve the counting problem as a regression task, i.e., given a single side-view image of the grapevine, the neural network predicts the number of its leaves.

Figure 20: Architecture of the deep neural network model used to solve the counting leaves problem.

Figure 20 shows the architecture of the deep neural network we employed to count the plant leaves. In detail, from left to right, the input image of the grapevine goes through several blocks (eight) of convolutional and max-pooling layers followed by three feedforward layers aimed to produce the final prediction, i.e., the actual number of leaves of the plant in the image. Deep neural network (DNN) solutions are well-known to be “data hungry” in order to effectively train complex models. Here, the application of DNN is made possible due to the availability of a dataset consisting of more than 250,000 images (~3 TeraBytes of data). Dataset images of grapevine plants are preprocessed before feeding the neural network. Top-view images are discarded because they are useless for the task, while side-view images are at first cropped maintaining only the central part where the plant is observed, and then the resolution is lowered as to diminish the computational cost for the neural network to extract useful patterns from the images (see Figure 21).

Figure 21: Preprocessing operations performed on each side-view image: cropping and down-scaling.

Each dataset is split into training, validation and test on a per-plant basis (i.e., all the images regarding a single plant are in a single fold) with a 60%, 20%, 20% proportion, respectively. Training fold is used to fit the model, while validation fold is used for early stopping the training when overfit starts to occur and for hyper-parameters tuning. Finally, test fold is used to collect model performance, mainly in terms of Mean Absolute

Error (MAE) and Mean Squared Error (MSE). Several neural network architectures have been tested (shape, size and number of layers), as well as different activation functions, optimization algorithms, and regularization techniques (e.g., batch regularizers, dropout). The architecture observed in Figure 20 is the one achieving the highest performance on the validation set in terms of the two metrics observed, and thus it has been chosen as the reference technical solution for solving the counting leaves task within the winemaking pilot.

The model has been trained on a machine equipped with two Intel(R) Xeon CPU E5-2630 v3 @ 2.40GHz (dual CPU, 8 cores with hyper-threading, 32 total concurrent threads), 192 GB of DD3 RAM, Nvidia TITAN Xp GPU (12 GB of GDDR5 memory, 3840 Nvidia CUDA cores). The neural network is characterized by 7,366,581 trainable parameters, and on the above machine its training took about 8 hours on the 2012 dataset, using 32,540 images for training and 10,870 images as validation for early stopping. Figure 22 shows the model performance during the training with the hyper-parameters selected. The training of the model took about 150 epochs to reach the optimal point on the validation set.

Figure 22: The performances of the model during the training on the 2012 dataset.

4.2.3 Analysis of the Performance

Table 3 shows the effectiveness of the model on the test set, compared to that of a trivial solution always predicting the mean number of leaves observed on the train fold. The mean absolute error proves that the developed solution is able to correctly count the number of leaves of each plant with an error lower than one leaf on average on the entire test fold. This result is not trivial even for a human. Indeed, the human annotation has been performed by observing the real plant live, not just by looking at the images. Moreover, leaves can overlap or some of them could be hidden by other leaves or by the trunk, thus making the task even more difficult.

Table 3: Performance of the model on the test set of the 2012 dataset.

	Model	Mean Absolute Error	Mean Squared Error
0	Mean Predictor	4.923	36.279
1	Deep Model	0.878	2.213

As to deepen our understanding on the performance of the model, we analyzed how the model behaves at the different percentiles of the number of leaves. Figure 23 reports a comparison between the predictions and the number of leaves for the different percentiles, showing that it performs very well in between percentiles 5 and 95, while making higher errors on the border, i.e., on images with a low/high number of leaves.

Figure 23: Performance of the model at different percentiles on the 2012 dataset.

We then analyzed how big the error is at the different percentiles in terms of mean absolute error (MAE). Figure 24 confirms the finding of Figure 23, showing that in between percentiles 1 and 95 the MAE is lower than a single leaf. As to assist the reader, the column identified by the label 5 reports the error made by the model on all the images with a number of leaves in the range [1-st percentile, 5-th percentile].

Figure 24: Mean Absolute Error of the model at different percentiles on the 2012 dataset.

Finally, we analyzed how big is the error at the different percentiles, by considering also whether the model underestimates or overestimates the correct number of leaves. Figure 25 reports that, on the images having a number of leaves lower than the 1-st percentile, the model overestimates the number of leaves by a bit more than two leaves. Similarly, but with an opposite and more evident behavior, on images having a number of leaves higher than the 99-th percentile, the model underestimates the number of leaves by around 4 leaves. The extent of each box reports how the error is distributed within the specific column. On images with a number

of leaves in the range [1-st percentile, 99-th percentile] the error is very small and well distributed between positive and negative values (i.e., underestimations and overestimations), with a mean error always lower than a single leaf.

Figure 25: Error of the model at different percentiles on the 2012 dataset.

4.3 FARM MANAGEMENT PILOT

Irrigation water has been and is still of major importance for farm management. In recent years, Smart Farming facilitates better farm management techniques by using Global Positioning Systems (GPS), Geographic Information Systems (GIS), remote sensing (RS) and variable rate application (VRA) technologies, providing economic benefits to growers in the form of reduced use of fertilizers, agrochemicals, and irrigation water, while having a positive environmental impact. In modern agriculture, water management requires the determination of the crop water requirement and time of irrigation to improve farm management. Crop water stress is key for optimizing irrigation. In viticulture, crop water stress measures the water shortage in vines and is derived based on plant canopy characteristics and air temperature, among others. Water stress affects in a direct way plant growth and development, however, plant responses to water deficit situations can be vine-species and stress-intensity specific. Thus, water stress prediction is an important task in farm management as it allows to monitor the amount of water that is easily usable by the vine. As a matter of fact, due to roots and plant structure, all the water contained in the soil is not completely useful to the plant. Among the total amount usable, there is a percentage, that can vary from cultivar to cultivar, under which the plant suffers for water scarcity, closing stems and reducing photosynthesis activity till dying. The water stress prediction is calculated on water balance based on reservoir. The reservoir is the soil with a certain amount of available water capacity. From this amount of water, we have losses represented by evapotranspiration and percolation, and gains represented mainly by precipitations and irrigation.

In this pilot, we study and develop a machine learning analytics for water balance prediction using meteorological data from weather stations and soil data.

4.3.1 Software Architecture

For this pilot, we have designed and developed the software architecture shown in Figure 26. The architecture is mainly composed of three components: Data Layer, Analytic API and the Decision Support Interface. At the Data Layer component, we find the data preprocessors that are in charge of acquiring and preprocessing data for the further analytic tasks. The Analytic API performs the water balance prediction from weather data and soil data. The water balance estimator can then be queried to provide predictions to the decision support systems.

Figure 26: Pilot 3, Software Architecture.

All components have been developed using python version 3. Specifically, the data preprocessors use the pandas python library (pandas.pydata.org) to load csv. The machine learning models have been implemented with sklearn (<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>).

4.3.2 Machine Learning for Water Balance Prediction

We develop a machine-learning component that performs water balance prediction using meteorological data from weather stations and soil data. The analysis has been performed on two fields under study by the BigDataGrapes project. The two fields are the “Casato Prime Donne” and “Il Palazzo”. The two fields have been equipped with two weather and soil stations that record several information at different levels of granularity. Data from the weather stations are collected by ABACO.

The data employed in this study have been gathered from 01, February 2019 to 10, January 2020 for the two fields. The first one, i.e., “Casato Prime Donne”, is composed of 373 observations. Each observation is described by a total of 35 features, i.e., columns containing specific values or aggregations of the value (max, min, sum, avg). The second one, i.e., “Il Palazzo”, is a dataset composed of 483 observations. The set of features is the same of the first one, i.e., 35 features. In details, the features available are:

The temperature of the air at 1,80 meters (3 aggregated features, avg, max, min)

- HC Air Temperature [°C]

The precipitation amount on a given period (1 feature, sum)

- Precipitation [mm]

The thermal Infrared temperature of the leaf or bunches surfaces (6 aggregated features, avg, max, min)

- Leaf Temperature (IR) [°C]

The percentage of water content in the soil from 0 to 50 cm (6 features, data taken every ten cm)

- EAG Soil Moisture [%], 0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 cm

The temperature of the soil from 0 to 50 cm (18 aggregated features, avg, max, min, data taken every ten cm)

- Soil Temperature [°C], 0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 cm

Daily amount of potential evapotranspiration. It is referred to the amount of water consumed by a reference grass of *festuca pratensis*.

- DailyETo

We perform a preliminary preprocessing of the data aiming at removing observations with NaNs. Each observation comes with a label, i.e., the water balance, reporting the availability of water for the specific field. This value is not normalized between different fields and it is expressed in mm/m (mm of water for each meter of soil). As a consequence, the label has been normalized in a $[0,1]$ range. The final number of observations after the preprocessing step is 171 (from 01, May 2019 to 18, October 2019) for “Casato Prime Donne” while it consists of 183 observations for “Il Palazzo”. After preprocessing, the two datasets are still described by 35 features.

We first apply a set of machine learning techniques for solving the following regression task: given an observation, predict its associated water level. The problem has been modeled by employing:

- linear models,
- regularized linear models, i.e., ridge, bayesian ridge and lasso,
- ensemble of tree-based models, i.e., gradient-boosted regression trees, random forests,
- voting methods,
- SVM regressor,
- neural networks.

For all the methods, we employ a standard k-fold cross validation methodology (with $k = 5$). K-fold cross validation first shuffles all 354 observations, then splits the dataset in five different folds, each one containing 20% of the observations. The methodology allows testing on a different test fold for five times each solution. The final performance reported is the average of the five performances on the test sets. The validation set is used for performing early stopping of the training of the models in order to avoid overfitting the data. In details, whenever it is possible to apply early stopping, e.g., for ensembles of trees, the training ends once the performance on the validation does not improve for up to a given number of iterations/epochs. In our methodology, we employ an early stopping of 10 iterations. Table 4 reports the results of the different predictors. We compare the different techniques using RMSE and we report the cross-validation score, i.e., the average over the five folds of the RMSE, plus the variance, i.e., the stability of the performance across the five runs. The best performance is achieved using a Random Forest regressor (RF). The performance of RF is very similar to another tree-based technique, i.e., Gradient Boosting regressor. We note that the latter shows a larger variance with respect to the former one. This can be explained with the well-known robustness to overfitting of the RF estimator. The third best-scoring technique is the MLP regressor, a multi-layer perceptron neural network. The network employed is a dense four layers network with two hidden layers of 50 and 25 neurons. We train it with Adam and a learning rate of $1e-5$ for 1000 epochs. Note that, as for tree-based models, we also employ early stopping on a validation set. SVM-based regression achieves a higher error than the one reported for the neural network. However, it is characterized by a very low variance of the results on the five folds of the dataset. Voting methods and linear (regularized) models follow with an increased RMSE. In details, when employing linear models, the error significantly increases on the test set showing that the such kinds of models are too simple to effectively distill the salient properties of the data.

Table 4: Performance of different machine learning techniques.

	Model	RMSE	STD DEV
5	RandomForestRegressor	0.090660	0.046008
6	GradientBoostingRegressor	0.090814	0.050801
8	MLPRegressor	0.113589	0.068620
4	SVR	0.119413	0.024910
7	VotingRegressor	0.133060	0.074512
3	BayesianRidge	0.202521	0.167365
1	Ridge	0.209393	0.165582
0	LinearRegression	0.216578	0.181374
2	Lasso	0.261249	0.045648

To better understand the dynamics that allows us to achieve the performance above, we perform a feature importance test by using the two models that achieve the lowest error on the test set, i.e., Random Forest and Gradient Boosting regressors. Feature importance is an analysis that allows to understand what features on average contribute the most to the reduction of the error, i.e., the importance that they have in producing the final prediction.

Figure 27: Feature importance of Random Forest regressor.

Figure 27 reports the analysis for the Random Forest regressor. The analysis shows that one feature, i.e., EAG Soil Moisture (10 cm) provides a strong contribution to the prediction with a normalized contribution of up to 0,40. It means that this feature alone contributes to the prediction for up to 40%. The following features, from the second position up to the fifth are all signals modeling soil, air or leaf temperatures. This is not surprising as we expect a strong correlation between the temperature observed in the soil, leaf and air with respect to the desired target, i.e., a water balance that captures an indication of water availability. From the fifth position on, we find several other soil-related signals that model moistures and, again, temperatures. As confirmed by the analysis, these signals are less important and for some of them this was already expected by looking at the properties. For example, some of these less important signals capture the dynamics of the moisture on the ground (EAG Soil Moisture (0 cm)). These signals are expected to be less correlated with a direct information of water availability as they are taken directly on the ground, where the water availability is a function of many other factors, or deep in the ground, e.g., 50 cm, where again, the information could not well reflect what is happening recently from a water availability point of view. Figure 28 provides the same analysis on the Gradient Boosting regressor. Here, things are similar as the first feature is the same used by the Random Forest model. However, in the case of the Gradient Boosting regressor, the importance of the first feature is even higher as it scores 0,55 in terms of normalized total importance. Moreover, from the second position on, we highlight differences in the importance of the features used. However, the first five features, although they show a different ranking in the list, are the same thus confirming the importance of signals measuring the soil moisture and the air, soil, and leaves temperatures to achieve a good prediction power of the trained model.

Figure 28: Feature importance of Gradient Boosting regressor.

4.4 NATURAL COSMETICS PILOT

Bioactive compounds found in wine making by-products such as vine leaves possess multifunctional characteristics and show a wide range of potential and remunerative applications, concerning health promoting activities. Nevertheless, the quality of these by-products and more specifically their biological efficacy can vary depending on multiple parameters, such as the origin of the sample, the recovery process and more.

In this pilot, we investigate how the biological activity depends on the location of the vineyard, the agriculture practices followed, the extraction method used, and the variety of the grape. The data collected from the natural cosmetics pilot provides the necessary information for the evaluation of the quality of each sample, linked with the special characteristics of the vineyard of origin. Particularly, we developed a solution that uses relevant properties of the biological efficacy and correlates them with vegetation indexes derived from earth observations obtained from satellite imagery systems.

4.4.1 Software Architecture

Besides providing relevant insights for farmers, the correlation analyses of Biological Activity characteristics with the vineyard’s vegetation indexes will also point out which information should be considered for building the machine learning models that will support the Decision Support Systems.

Thus, the goal is to develop an analytic module that handles the biological activity data providing useful information for the decision-making process of industry end-users and practitioners. Figure 29 exhibits the main components of the software architecture developed: Data Layers, Analytic API, and Decision Support Interface. In brief, the Data Layer component is in charge of parsing and crawling the Biologic Activity data, with both Maceration and Ultrasound properties, and also the Satellite Imagery data, more specifically the vegetation indexes. The Analytic API performs associations and correlations between the biologic activity properties and satellite imagery indexes (satellite data layer). The Decision Support Interface can then query the Analytic API to obtain the correlation results.

Figure 29: Pilot 4, Software Architecture.

From the technology background, similarly to the Pilot 1 software stack, all components have been developed in python version 3. Specifically, the data parsers for the BA data have been developed using the pandas python library (pandas.pydata.org) to load csv and Excel files content, while the python library requests

(requests.readthedocs.io/) have been used to build the crawlers for consuming Satellite Imagery data from the Geocledian API (geocledian.com/agknow/api/v3/). To compute the Pearson correlation coefficient the Analytic API uses numpy (numpy.org/) for efficient processing. The REST web service was developed using flask (flask.palletsprojects.com/en/1.1.x/). For a quick visualization of the heatmaps with the correlation values, we have used seaborn library (seaborn.pydata.org/) on top of python notebooks.

4.4.2 Natural Cosmetics data

The preparation of vine leaf extracts, i.e., maceration and ultrasound assisted extraction, and testing of their biological efficacy for each sample took place at the laboratory of Symbeeosis Company APIVITA S.A. – Natural Cosmetics, located in Industrial Park of Markopoulo Mesogaïas in Greece. At the laboratory, extractions are conducted under the two different methods and the following measurements of biological activity are made: pH, RI, TPC, TFC, Total Microbial Count, Yeasts & Moulds, DPPH & ABTS assay. For BA (Biological activity), for both maceration and ultrasound assisted extractions, the following features are considered:

- **pH** of vine leaf extracts
- **Refractive index (%)**. Refractive index of vine leaf extracts
- Antioxidant activity **DPPH** and **ABTS** ($\mu\text{g/mL}$ trolox) of vine leaf extracts
- Total phenolic content, **TPC** ($\mu\text{g/mL}$ gallic acid) of vine leaf extracts
- Total flavonoid content, **TFC** ($\mu\text{g/mL}$ quercetin) of vine leaf extracts

By using the Geocledian API (<https://sites.google.com/site/geocledian/documentation>), a crawler collects the time series of different available indexes for the 9 parcels under study. We have considered 8 numeric satellite imagery indexes provided by the Geocledian API as features:

- **NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index)**. Quantifies vegetation by measuring the difference between near-infrared (which vegetation strongly reflects) and red light (which vegetation absorbs). Overall, NDVI is a standardized way to measure healthy vegetation. When you have high NDVI values, you have healthier vegetation. When you have low NDVI, you have less or no vegetation.
- **NDRE1 (Normalized Difference Red Edge Index (v1))**. Substitution of NDVI's red band with NDRE's red edge band provides a measurement that is not as strongly absorbed by just the topmost layers of leaves.
- **NDRE2 (Normalized Difference Red Edge Index (v2))**. Substitution of NDVI's red band with NDRE's red edge band (700nm).
- **NDWI (Normalized Difference Water Index)**. NDWI is less susceptible to atmospheric scattering than NDVI, but does not completely remove the background soil reflectance effects, similar to NDVI.
- **SAVI (Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index)**. The index is a transformation technique that minimizes soil brightness influences from spectral vegetation indices involving red and near-infrared (NIR) wavelengths.
- **EVI2 (Enhanced Vegetation Index 2)**. The enhanced vegetation index (EVI) is an optimized vegetation index designed to enhance the vegetation signal with improved sensitivity in high biomass regions and improved vegetation monitoring through a de-coupling of the canopy background signal and a reduction in atmosphere influences.
- **CI-RE (Chlorophyll Index - Red Edge)**. The chlorophyll index is used to calculate the total chlorophyll content of the leaves. The C_{green} and C_{red-edge} values are sensitive to small variations in the chlorophyll content and consistent across most species.

We used a total of 9 fields as a study case for the correlation analysis between the two data layers. All fields are located in Greece. Table 5 shows the location of the fields.

Table 5: Wineries of samples included in correlation analysis for Pilot 4.

#	Sample ID	Vineyard	Variety	Region	City	Parcel ID
1	I.A.1	RIRA Vineyards	Agiorgitiko	Peloponnese	Aigio	135973
2	I.A.2	Semeli Wines	Agiorgitiko	Peloponnese	Nemea	135939
3	I.M.4	Moraitis Winery	Mandilaria	Aegean	Paros	136162
4	I.A.5	Pavlidis Estate	Agiorgitiko	Northern Greece	Drama	135947
5	I.A.8	Biblia Chora Estate	Agiorgitiko	Northern Greece	Kavala	136168
6	I.M.9	Toplou Winery	Mandilaria	Crete	Sitia	136164
7	I.A.10	Skouras Domaine	Agiorgitiko	Peloponnese	Argos	136159
8	I.M.11	Aoton Winery	Mandilaria	Attica	Peania	136167
9	I.A.13	Papagiannakos Domaine	Agiorgitiko	Attica	Markopoulo	136169

4.4.3 Correlation Analysis on Natural Cosmetics data

The idea is that we can collect insights of how these properties correlate between them crossing data from the different vineyards. For the correlation task, we use the available features at the data layers to create vectors of size $F \times T$, where F are the number of fields and T is the number of temporal points considered for the analysis. Since most of the data have been collected from the last two year (2018 and 2019), for most of the analysis reported in this document we have T equals 2. We have used Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients to perform the correlation analysis.

The two layers have different periodicity on the collection of their features. For example, new BA records are collected yearly, while the satellite images are taken almost weekly. For this reason, we use different aggregation functions and time frames for the satellite imagery indexes. We use the following time frame to filter the satellite data for aggregation: from the beginning of the year of crop until end of $\langle month \rangle$ (of the same year), having *March, April, May* and *June* as possible values. Then, as an aggregation function, we use minimum (min), maximum (max), mean, standard deviation (std), count and sum.

Currently, the Analytic API manages two scenarios for the correlation analysis involving the two data layers of this pilot:

- correlations between biological activity (BA) for maceration features and satellite image indexes.
- correlations between BA for ultrasound features and satellite image indexes.

The API resource *maceration* handles associations and correlations between BA for maceration features and satellite image indexes.

Figure 30 shows an example of a heatmap plot fed by the correlation values retrieved by the *maceration* API resource. We can observe that the highest positive correlation between the BA data (on axis y) and satellite layer (on axis x) was seen for the properties *NDRE3* index and the *TPC metric* with a Pearson coefficient of 0.55. The heatmap also shows a relevant negative correlation of -0,712 between the features *CIRE* and *pH*.

Figure 30: Heatmap visualization of the insights provided by the API resource: *maceration*.

The API resource *ultrasound* handles associations and correlations between BA for ultrasound features and satellite image indexes.

Figure 31 now shows the heatmap plot from values retrieved from the ultrasound API resource. Through the Figure we can observe that for the year of observation (i.e., 2018) many relevant correlations are both positive and negative. The BA feature (on axis y) TFC presents a very high positive correlation with almost all satellite indexes. The same for the feature DPPH, but now showing a high negative correlation with almost all the satellite indexes.

Figure 31: Heatmap visualization of the insights provided by the API resource: *ultrasound*.

4.5 FOOD PROTECTION PILOT

Food protection, including safety and fraud, is one of the most critical parameters in food production which highly affects the food companies from the financial and brand point of view. This pilot aims to enhance the current digital provided in FOODAKAI with new modules that address further needs of the grape and wine supply chain. The enhancement will mainly focus on the further development of Agroknow’s Big Data platform with new software modules that will enable advanced data analysis and risk prediction using machine learning and deep learning methods.

In this pilot, we tackle novel applications of the grape and wine supply chain with new software modules that will enable advanced data analysis, risk and predictions using machine learning and deep learning methods. In particular, we present three novel analytics built on top of the AgroKnow Big Data platform. The three analytics aims at solving three tasks, i.e., i) price prediction, ii) recall prediction, and iii) risk assessment. The first two tasks have been solved through the application of supervised techniques for regression while the risk estimation has been computed with a simple yet effective mathematical approach.

4.5.1 Price prediction

The specific goal of the price prediction is to develop a software module that allows to predict the future price of specific goods in the grapes and wines supply chain. Starting from past observations of the price of different agro/food items, we build a machine learning pipeline that allows us to experiment with several prediction solutions.

4.5.1.1 Software Architecture

Figure 32 shows the software architecture developed to this pilot: Data Layers, Price Prediction API, and Decision Support Interface. In brief, the Data Layer component is in charge of parsing and crawling the historical prices of products over the countries. The Price Prediction API performs the prediction of the next day price of a given product. Decision support systems can then query the Price prediction API to obtain the forecast results.

Figure 32: Pilot 5, Software Architecture.

All components have been developed using python version 3. Specifically, the data preprocessors use the pandas python library (pandas.pydata.org) to load csv and the python Keras library (<https://keras.io/>). The deep learning models have been implemented with Keras.

4.5.1.2 Historical Product Prices

We build our datasets starting from the open data published by the governments. The data used are collected from the Hellenic Food Market, the European Commission and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. The dataset consists of a collection of daily observations of prices for a variety of products available in different countries. First, we assess the coverage of the products for different countries. The top-10 countries represented in the dataset are reported in Table 6.

Table 6: Top 10 countries by number of products in the dataset.

Country	# Products
Greece	261
Europe	125
Belgium	85
Portugal	71
Austria	63
Estonia	56
Poland	48
Spain	47
Germany	46
Italy	45

A big portion of the data comes from Greece while Europe is the second most-popular country. Clearly, in this category falls all the products that do not have specified the country of origin. In total, the dataset records 61,000 price variations of 1,356 products coming from different EU countries.

We perform a standard data preprocessing aiming at removing non-number values, duplicated rows and columns. After this preprocessing, we perform some basic plotting of our target feature, i.e., price. Figure 33 shows the population (y-axis) of price samples in the data using a histogram plot with 200 bins. It is easy to see that the majority of samples are lower than 200 Euro (x-axis). The mean of the price samples is 164.60 with a standard deviation of 142.40 Euro. Moreover, the median is 152.50 Euro and 75% of the samples are lower than 234.78 Euro.

Figure 33: Histogram plot of price samples with 200 bins.

4.5.1.3 Machine Learning for Price Prediction

In this pilot, we employ time series, i.e., sequences of per-product price observations, to learn a machine learning system that allows us to predict the future price of the product, given an historical time window. Time series prediction is a well-known task that is commonly addressed using neural networks. In particular, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) are a specific kind of neural network that learns the properties of sequences of objects to predict their evolution. We employ Long Short-term memory (LSTM) networks to address this task. LSTM is a powerful RNN architecture with important application in time series prediction. For the development of the LSTM in our component, we used the python Keras library.

We addressed the task as a regression problem, where, given a sequence of daily observations of prices, we want to predict the price that will be seen in the next day. Unfortunately, we have not been able to apply the LSTM on the whole datasets. The time series of a large number of products have holes, i.e., portions of the series with no available data. We thus apply heuristics to select the time series useful for learning our LSTM. First, we select from the dataset the time series with at least 100 points. This condition has been strengthened by also including the time series with less than seven days with no price information. Then, we end up with a total of 14 products. For some products, the combination of the two conditions does not allow to have contiguous information. In these cases, we apply forward fill to fill the missing data. The problem of using forward fill is that we are not using “real” data. Indeed, we are filling some holes with an a-priori assumption, i.e., the missing price is the same as a few days ago, that can lead to errors in the prediction. This is why we limit the maximum number of days with no price observations to seven. In this way, we intend to limit the error introduced in the data.

With the data above, we design the neural network architecture, which we find to be a LSTM network composed of one LSTM layer with 150 neurons. The output layer of the network is a neuron with no activation that is in charge of producing the final price prediction, i.e., the regression of the price on the data provided as input. We learned the network with a standard train-test methodology by splitting the filtered dataset of time series in 70% (train) and 30% (test). Moreover, the loss used to learn the network is mean squared error (MSE)

and the Adam optimizer with learning rate 0.01. We also employ early stopping to stop the learning of the network for 1000 epochs when no error reduction is observed on the validation set for more than 50 epochs. We then evaluate the performance of the LSTM on the test set, i.e., we provide a time window of data and the network outputs the price prediction that is then matched on the test time series to compute the error. Table 7 reports the top-5 best predictive products.

Table 7: Top-5 best predictive performance.

model_name	product_name	mean_squared_error	root_mean_squared_error	mean_absolute_error
lstm_fforward	πατάτες εισαγ	0.000056	0.007452	0.002171
lstm_fforward	πατάτες εγγ.	0.000086	0.009291	0.004236
lstm_fforward	piglet	0.239190	0.489070	0.370312
lstm_fforward	pig carcasses 55% or more but less than 60% meat	0.559596	0.748062	0.509527
lstm_fforward	pig carcasses with 60% or more meat	0.664141	0.814948	0.625653

The five products above are characterized by a very low mean squared error, i.e., the prediction produced is close to the actual price observed in the data. We then plot the prediction of the price (Figure 34) for the five products by varying the time.

Figure 34: Performance on the top-5 best predictions.

The five plots above show an interesting performance of our LSTM. The first, best performing product shows a very low average price. For this product in particular, the task of predicting the next price could achieve low error just because the price is always very low, and the final error is thus low. Indeed, this intuition is confirmed by the evolution of the prediction. While in the first part of the predicted curve the prediction is close to the target value, in the second part of the prediction the system shows high relative error between the two lines thus confirming the guess. However, a different behavior is achieved on the other predictions where our LSTM model well fits the data and allows for effective predictions with small relative error between the predicted and the real target value.

We extend the analysis above on the worse prediction products. Now, we use the learned model to list the top-5 products with highest error on the test set. Table 8 shows the 5 products with the worst prediction performance.

Table 8: Top-5 worst predictive products.

model_name	product_name	mean_squared_error	root_mean_squared_error	mean_absolute_error
lstm_fforward	lampante olive oil (2°)	38.716873	6.222288	4.671025
lstm_fforward	virgin olive oil (up to 2°)	71.180071	8.436828	4.562842
lstm_fforward	crude olive-pomace oil (from 5 to 10°)	74.158953	8.611559	6.680811
lstm_fforward	refined olive-pomace oil (up to 0.3°)	138.282895	11.759375	9.054137
lstm_fforward	extra virgin olive oil (up to 0,8°)	295.252883	17.182924	11.852230

We are interested in inspecting the reasons why we achieve such a bad performance. For this reason, we plot the prediction as before to visually inspect the results. Figure 35 reports the performance of the LSTM for the five products above by varying the time.

Figure 35: Performance on the top-5 worst predictions.

The five plots above partially explain how our model sometimes does not provide effective prediction. First, we highlight that all the five products are characterized by very high prices. This is expected as small differences in the prediction leads to high RMSE. Moreover, the five products are characterized by time series with irregular trends, i.e., the price is affected by a high variability. This leads to errors as a correct prediction is always difficult on data with high variance.

To better evaluate the performance of our LSTM on the test set, we propose a comparison against a strong baseline (Table 9). The baseline we are proposing is always employed in time series analysis and prediction because it provides a way to compare the performance of a predictor against the performance of a price produced using the moving average of the previous observed prices. Here, we compare our LSTM against a moving average baseline that employs the last 15 observations of the price. When considering the average of the root mean squared error between the real price and the predicted one the LSTM achieves a total error that is worse than the baseline. However, this is due to errors achieved on specific products (see Table 10Table 8). In details, LSTM is able to outperform the baseline for most of the products and the average performance is worsened by the high error observed for two products in particular, i.e., "extra virgin olive oil (up to 0,8°)" and "refined olive-pomace oil (up to 0.3°).

Table 9: Mean RMSE error for the price prediction forecast of all products.

model_name	mean_squared_error	root_mean_squared_error	mean_absolute_error
moving_avg	40.538	4.019	2.721
lstm_forward	46.188	4.461	3.139

Table 10: RMSE error for the price prediction forecast of each product.

product_name	root_mean_squared_error_bas	root_mean_squared_error_lstm	improvement(%)
pig carcasses with 60% or more meat	1.749	0.815	114.578
pig carcasses 55% or more but less than 60% meat	1.594	0.748	113.145
maize - maize deliver to first customer - silo or processing plant - on truck or other transport means	2.714	1.396	94.333
πατάτες εγχ.	0.015	0.009	59.841
virgin olive oil (up to 2°)	13.376	8.437	58.548
piglet	0.765	0.489	56.429
soft wheat - milling wheat delivered to port - grain delivered to a port silo by train or truck or barge	2.929	2.220	31.916
refined olive oil (up to 0,3°)	4.689	4.550	3.041
extra virgin olive oil (up to 0,8°)	17.382	17.183	1.161
πατάτες εισαγ	0.007	0.007	0.000
lampante olive oil (2°)	4.628	6.222	0.000
crude olive-pomace oil (from 5 to 10°)	2.787	8.612	0.000
refined olive-pomace oil (up to 0.3°)	3.626	11.759	0.000

4.5.2 Recall prediction

The specific goals of the recall prediction task are to develop a software module to predict food recalls and border rejections on an annual basis in the grapes and wines supply chain. Furthermore, we tested different prediction approaches. Working with real industry scenarios, we define which are the main parameters that need to be predicted.

Based on these findings we test several machine learning and deep learning algorithms presented in Figure 36 and combine different datasets to achieve the optimum performance for the prediction of the recall in raw materials and finished products. A large number of different data sources and data types have been used to enable the predictions. We mainly used textual information including announcements about food recalls and border rejections. The main source of our datasets is the open data published by the governments.

Figure 36: AI algorithms Tested.

Moreover, in order to find the best prediction model for practical use, the standard approach is to try the above predictive methods on the data set of interest and then pick the best performing method and fine-tune it for use as the predictor tool. This approach was also followed in these experiments presented above. In machine learning those configurations of parameters, that are external to the model and are not learned from data, are called hyperparameters, for example the number of hidden layers in neural networks. Hyperparameters must be optimized by cross-validation or grid search to make a balance between variance and bias in prediction. Below we refer to the procedure of selecting algorithms based on different datasets. The purpose of this process is to select 4 algorithms that have the best results and test them on different datasets. Then, the 4 algorithms are re-examined with differential data sizes in order to select the one with the best results in the majority of cases.

4.5.2.1 First approach: testing algorithms on generic product categories

The purpose of these experiments is to test the algorithms presented above in data consisting of recalls and border rejections grouped by product category. Using the recalls and border rejections data of the previous 20 years, we validated the prediction capabilities of the best model for the year 2019 and using the best model we created a forecast for 2020. So, for which ingredient categories the recalls and border rejections will increase? After a lot of experiments in which every product was tested with each algorithm, we conclude that K-nearest neighbors, Decision tree, long short-term memory networks, and the Prophet algorithm, i.e., an additive regression procedure, have the best results. According to the results presented in Table 11, there will be a small increase in nuts and nuts products, fruits and vegetables, non-alcoholic beverages, and a larger increase in cereals and bakery products as well in the chocolate products.

Table 11: Prediction results per product category based on best algorithms results.

Ingredient category	What happened in 2019	What our best algorithm predicted for 2019	What will happen in 2020	Trend
Nuts and nuts products	706	698 (93% KNN)	722	+2%
Non-alcoholic beverages	184	187 (98% Decision Tree)	188	+2%
Cereals and Bakery products	665	661 (96% LSTM)	760	+14%
Milk and milk products	316	267 (84% LSTM)	307	-3%
Chocolate products	102	91 (89% LSTM)	110	+8%
Fruits and vegetables	1170	1228 (97% Prophet)	1198	+2%
Herbs and Spices	587	449 (75% LSTM)	502	-15%
Ice creams	44	65 (54% LSTM)	64	+45%

4.5.2.2 Second approach: predicting hazards for each product category using the best algorithms

The purpose of these experiments is to test the algorithms that had better results in smaller data consisting of recalls and border rejections for a specific hazard per product category. Based on previous results we select KNN, Decision Tree, LSTM and Prophet. For each product category we tested all the previous results in order to predict the number of each hazard for the next year. The tables below present the accuracy for each algorithm per specific hazard.

Table 12: Accuracy results for nuts and nuts products for 2019.

Hazards	KNN	Decision Tree	LSTM	Prophet
Chemical	81%	80%	79%	85%
Biological	67%	65%	69%	77%
Fraud	64%	72%	70%	82%

Table 13: Accuracy results for fruits and vegetables for 2019.

Hazards	KNN	Decision Tree	LSTM	Prophet
Chemical	86%	80%	90%	95%
Biological	69%	72%	83%	87%

Table 14: Accuracy results for cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea for 2019.

Hazards	KNN	Decision Tree	LSTM	Prophet
Chemical	82%	80%	88%	97%
Biological	80%	78%	83%	93%

From the above results we conclude that Deep Learning algorithms and in particular Prophet have better results. Moreover, for smaller size data almost no algorithm had proper results. In the “Nuts and nuts Products” (Table 12) product category the majority of hazards are chemical, biological and fraud. Comparing the results among the three hazards, it is observed that for chemicals, the algorithms predicted better results for 2019. Some results are observed in the “fruits and vegetables” (Table 13) and in the “cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea” (Table 14) product category. In both cases, the Prophet algorithm has better performance. Chemical and Biological hazards have almost the same volume of data and the accuracy in both cases are similar. The next approach relates to the testing of the above 4 algorithms and the data consisting of recall and border rejections grouped by industry case.

4.5.2.3 Third approach: testing algorithms on specific industry case

Industry-specific data were used in this approach. Focusing on a specific industry such as the chocolate industry, we see that the model can provide a good prediction for Coca and Peanuts indicating an increase in hazards (Table 15). For Hazelnuts, almonds and palm oil the accuracy was quite low and thus the forecast cannot be considered safe.

Table 15: Prediction results for choco industry case based on prophet's results.

Ingredient	What happened in 2019	What our best algorithm predicted for 2019	What will happen in 2020	Trend
Cocoa	22	24 (72%)	25	+14%
Peanuts	117	122 (95%)	132	+13%
Hazelnuts	40	44 (55%)	48	+20%
Almonds	70	104 (52%)	104	+48%
Palm oil	17	12 (68%)	13	-23%

Moreover, the models can help us to predict the trend of specific hazards for a specific ingredient like the peanuts. As we can observe in Table 16, the prophet model predicts that in 2020 there will be a 4% increase for aflatoxins in peanuts.

Table 16: Prediction results of specific hazard in peanuts based on prophet's results.

Hazards	What happened in 2019	What our best algorithm predicted for 2019	What will happen in 2020	Trend
Chemical	101	102 (97%)	102	0%
Mycotoxins	101	124 (77%)	102	0%
Aflatoxin	101	102 (98%)	106	+4%

Working with aflatoxin in peanuts, we applied the Prophet prediction model using data from 1997 until 2018. The prediction for 2019 indicated an increase of 31% of aflatoxin in peanuts although the number of incidents were decreasing in 2018 compared to 2017 (Figure 37). Such predictions for the trend of aflatoxin could be used by the company to prevent the rejection that costs a lot to the company.

Figure 37: Prediction results of aflatoxin in peanuts based on prophet's results.

Concluding, the prophet algorithm presents the best results in the majority of cases. Important factors that affect the results are the size of the data, the homogeneity of the product categories and the seasonality. The following plots (Figure 38) shows the results of the prophet algorithm for specific product categories for the next year.

Figure 38: Prophet projection per product category.

4.5.3 Risk Assessment module

The main goal of the risk assessment module is to help Food Safety Experts to identify the ingredients with unacceptable hazard risk. The risk for each ingredient is estimated in relation to a specific Hazard for this ingredient e.g., risk for aflatoxins in peanuts, risk for pesticides in peanuts, risk for salmonella in peanuts. The risk estimation is based on the frequency of the food safety incidents that the 5th pilot has collected and processed. It should be mentioned that the risk is continuously updated (live risk) every time that new food safety incidents are collected and processed by Agroknow.

The risk assessment module focuses both on the reputation of the company and on the impact of the specific hazard on the public health. Regarding the reputation the risk assessment model includes a severity factor which is based on how bad a specific type of notification is for the reputation of the company. The most severe is the recall of a product from the market. For what regards the hazard impact on the public health, we are using standard classification of the severity defined and used by agencies and authorities like the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) of the United States. All the details about the risk estimation are presented in the remaining of this section.

The following risk estimation formula is being used for the estimation of the risk

$$\text{Risk} = \text{Incident Severity} \times \text{Hazard Severity} \times \text{Probability}$$

where:

1. **Incident Severity:** is the severity based on the type of the incident (e.g., food recall, food alert, border rejection). A table with the severity classification values mapped to incident types is presented later in this document.
2. **Hazard Severity:** is the severity of the hazard based on the health impact. The hazard severity is classified as: 1, 2, 3 and follows the classification defined by organizations such as FDA. e.g., listeria spp=3, pesticide=2. Detailed values for the hazard severity are presented later in this document.
3. **Probability:** is the probability of the specific hazard to occur for the specific ingredient. The estimation of the probability is based on the frequency of the incidents that the Agroknow collects and processes every day.

Each of these parameters and the corresponding classifications used in FOODAKAI system are analyzed below.

4.5.3.1 Incident Severity

In Table 17, we present the classification used for the incident severity. The types of the incidents are based on official data sources such as the Rapid Alert for Food and Feed (RASFF).

Table 17: Risk estimation formula classification.

Incident type (Reputation oriented)	Value
Food Alert/ Recall	5
Border Rejection	4
Information	3
Information for attention	2
Information for follow up	1

For the estimation of the incident severity for each specific ingredient in a category we are using the mean value. For instance, if for aflatoxin and for pistachio there are 100 alerts, 120 border rejections and 10 information for attention the Severity = $(100*5+120*4+10*2)/230 = 4.34$

4.5.3.2 Hazard Severity

In Table 18 we present the classification of the hazard severity for the most important hazard categories. It should be pointed out that, in some cases, there are hazards that have different classification values than their category. For instance, in a category like Biological there are hazards such as coliforms and moulds that have a classification of 2 due to the fact that the health impact is lower. On the other hand, there may be cases that a specific hazard may have higher classification value than its category.

Table 18: Classification of the hazard severity.

Hazard Category	Value
Allergens	3
Biological	3
Chemical	2
Foreign bodies	2
Fraud	2
Organoleptic aspects	1

The classification that is used in Risk is based on the FDA’s classification of hazards depicted in the following table (Table 19).

Table 19: FDA’s classification of hazards.

Hazard Severity Classification	
3	This is a health hazard situation where there is a reasonable probability that the use of the product will cause serious, adverse health consequences or death.
2	This is a health hazard situation where there is a remote probability of adverse health consequences from the use of the product.
1	This is a situation where the use of the product will not cause adverse health consequences.

4.5.3.3 Probability

The probability is estimated with two different approaches.

1. **Approach 1:** The first approach is estimated as the fraction of the number of incidents for the specific ingredient and hazard to the total number of incidents for the specific ingredient.

$$P = \frac{\text{Number of incidents of a hazard for the specific ingredient}}{\text{Total number of incidents of hazards for the specific ingredient}}$$

2. **Approach 2:** The second approach focuses on the probability of a hazard for a specific ingredient to occur in the ingredient category that the ingredient belongs (e.g., a hazard to occur for okra that belongs to fruits and vegetables). It is estimated as the fraction of the number of incidents for the specific product and hazard to the total number of the incidents for the specific category of the ingredient and the specific hazard.

$$P = \frac{\text{Number of incidents of a hazard for the specific ingredient}}{\text{Total number of incidents of hazards for the specific ingredient category}}$$

The different approach for the estimation of the risk can be configured using the Risk Settings button in FOODAKAI as shown in Figure 39. Using the settings option, the expert can adjust also the time period for which the risk is estimated (3 or 5 years) and he can disable the incident type severity factor.

Edit Risk Settings - [learn more about the settings](#)

Detailed View ON
Select whether you want to view details for the risks of every ingredient of the product

Compute Risk for last 5 YEARS ▾
Select the last n years for which you want to view the risk of every product

Compute frequency of risk by number of incidents of INGREDIENT ▾
Select if you want the probability of the risk for every hazard per ingredient to be computed by the number of incidents for the ingredient or for the ingredient's category

Include severity factor based on incident type OFF
Select whether the type of the incident ('alert', 'border rejection', 'information', 'information for attention', 'information for follow-up') will affect the total risk

[CANCEL](#) [SAVE CHANGES](#)

Figure 39: FDA's classification of hazards.

4.5.3.4 How risk is classified

The estimated risk is classified as Low, Medium and High.

- 1- 15 = I - Low
- 16 - 24 = II - Low
- 25 - 48 = III - Medium
- 49 - 75 = IV - High

The estimated risk value is presented in the FOODAKAI system as shown in the following Figure 40.

Figure 40: Risk for your product.

All the potential values of the risk for the three dimensions, namely, hazard severity, incident severity and probability, are presented in the following matrices (Figure 41).

Hazard Severity=1					
	Probability				
Incident Severity	(1) Unlikely	(2) Small possibility	(3) Occasional	(4) Possible	(5) Frequent
I ^(Low)	I (1)	I (2)	I (3)	I (4)	I (5)
II	I (2)	I (4)	I (6)	I (8)	I (10)
III	I (3)	I (6)	I (9)	I (12)	I (15)
IV	I (4)	I (8)	I (12)	II (16)	II (20)
V ^(High)	I (5)	I (10)	I (15)	II (20)	III (25)

Hazard Severity=2					
	Probability				
Incident Severity	(1) Unlikely	(2) Small possibility	(3) Occasional	(4) Possible	(5) Frequent
I ^(Low)	I (2)	I (4)	I (6)	I (8)	I (10)
II	I (4)	I (8)	I (12)	II (16)	II (20)
III	I (6)	I (12)	II (18)	II (24)	III (30)
IV	I (8)	II (16)	II (24)	III (32)	III (40)
V ^(High)	I (10)	II (20)	III (30)	III (40)	IV (50)

Hazard Severity=3					
	Probability				
Incident Severity	(1) Unlikely	(2) Small possibility	(3) Occasional	(4) Possible	(5) Frequent
I ^(Low)	I (3)	I (6)	I (9)	I (12)	I (15)
II	I (6)	I (12)	II (18)	II (24)	III (30)
III	I (9)	II (18)	III (27)	III (36)	III (45)
IV	I (12)	II (24)	III (36)	III (48)	IV (60)
V ^(High)	I (15)	III (30)	III (45)	IV (60)	IV (75)

Figure 41: Risk for the three dimensions, i.e., hazard severity, incident severity and probability.

4.5.3.5 Tendency

We aim at providing the tendency of risk (percentage of change) by comparing the risk of the last 12 months (1 year) with the risk for the last 3 years and last 5 years. More specifically, for the case of the 3 years Risk, the system estimates the Risk of the last 12 months (Current Date - 1 year) and compares it to the Risk of 2 years before the last year. The formula for the estimation of the tendency is:

$$tendency = \frac{Risk\ for\ the\ period\ of\ the\ last\ 12\ months - Risk\ for\ the\ period\ of\ N - 12\ months}{Risk\ for\ the\ period\ of\ the\ last\ N - 12\ months} \%$$

where **N** = 36 months or 60 months. If the tendency is negative, then we have a decrease while if the tendency is positive, we have an increase of the risk.

4.6 FINAL NOTES ON SOURCE CODE

The demonstrators of the five pilots have been released as source code on the project's GitHub repository. Interested readers can refer to Section 3.3 to learn how to get the code. The material of each pilot has been grouped in a specific directory containing source code of the demonstrators (as Jupyter notebook). Below, we report the structure of the directories and the entry point of each pilot. Each directory also contains the source code of the API that has been developed to allow the integration of the machine learning components within the BigDataGrapes architecture.

- Pilot1-TableWineGrapes/D4.3-CorrelationAnalysis-TableWineGrapes-Pilot1.ipynb
- Pilot2-WineQuality/D4.3-CountingLeaves-Pilot2.ipynb
- Pilot3-FarmManagement/D4.3-WaterBalancePrediction-Pilot3.ipynb
- Pilot4-NaturalCosmetics/D4.3-CorrelationAnalysis-NaturalCosmetics-Pilot4.ipynb
- Pilot5-FoodProtection/D4.3-PricePrediction-Pilot5.ipynb
- Pilot5-FoodProtection/D4.3-RecallPrediction-Pilot5.ipynb
- Pilot5-FoodProtection/D4.3-RiskAssessment.ipynb

5 SUMMARY

This accompanying document for deliverable D4.3 (Models and Tools for Predictive Analytics over Extremely Large Datasets) describes the first version of the mechanisms and tools supporting efficient and effective predictive data analytics over the BigDataGrapes (BDG) platform in the context of grapevine-related assets.

The BDG software stack employs efficient and fault-tolerant tools for distributed processing, aimed at providing scalability and reliability for the target applications. On top of this stack, the BDG platform enables distributed predictive big data analytics by effectively exploiting scalable Machine Learning algorithms using the computational resources of the underlying infrastructure efficiently. The software components enabling BDG predictive data analytics have been designed and deployed using Docker containers. They thus include everything needed to run the supported predictive data analytics tools on any system that can run a Docker engine.

In this first version of D4.3 we assessed the effectiveness of different predictive data analytics tools on very simple datasets in terms of standard and popular metrics such as Accuracy. In the updates delivered at M15, we added a rich and complex analysis of a large dataset of wine reviews highlighting the potentiality of the BDG tools used to assess the potential market penetration of a given wine in a new country. We estimate this penetration capability by learning a model from a very large dataset of user-generated wine content containing 489,417 wine reviews by 195,678 users, written in 86 languages, related to 51,579 different wines, from 58 wine countries and 2272 wine regions.

The final version of this deliverable submitted at M31 presents the analytics developed to support the competence questions of the five BigDataGrapes pilots. For each pilot, we: i) detail the specific task we addressed, ii) present a description of the software architecture of the analytics developed, iii) describe the data acquisition and preprocessing pipeline employed to train and apply the models within the BigDataGrapes infrastructure, iv) present the machine-learning techniques that we employ to solve the task, the methodology used and the hyper-parameter tuning performed to provide the best performance to the BigDataGrapes final user. For each technique, we also provide an experimental analysis of the techniques evaluated against strong baselines and state-of-the-art competitors on the data provided within the BDG consortium.